

DEVELOPMENT OF AN OPTIMIZATION METHOD FOR COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY : A method for determining the optimal direction and volume fraction of fibers at each point of a structure is developed. It results in a curved fiber format which exhibits variable stiffness properties. The fiber orientation and the fiber volume fraction are assumed to be constant within each element of the finite element model, but they vary from element to element. A convergent algorithm is obtained using variational formulations. It consists in two alternating minimizations : a local one and a global one. The particular case of panels in plane stresses is presented. Numerical applications for laminates subjected to an edge load are presented.

KEYWORDS : Fiber-reinforced composites, optimization, variable stiffness, curvilinear fibers, finite-element, variational formulation.

INTRODUCTION

It is possible to have a laminate which responds favorably to a prescribed loading condition by combining layers with various material properties, fibers orientations, and fibers volume fraction. Traditional design considers these lamina properties to be constant throughout the entire ply. However, it is desirable to consider ways to further tailor the design of composite materials so that the resulting structures will offer an advantage over current practices (such as lighter weight, reduced manufacturing cost, and so on). Recent developments in manufacturing techniques such as the tow placement machine [1, 2, 3] make it possible to fabricate composite structure that have spacially variable fibers volume ratio and fibers orientation within a single layer. For flat panels, it results in a curved fiber format, which exhibits variable stiffness properties. The response of laminates composed

of layers with fiber orientation varying along one direction has been studied earlier by Giirdal and Olmedo[4]. Hyer and Lee [5] have developed finite element models of panels with curvilinear fiber format, by varying the fiber angle from one region of the plate to another, and using a gradient-search technique.

The interest for this work, is to optimize the response of a lamina under prescribed loads by varying at once the volume ratio and the orientation of the fibers within the lamina. A finite-element discretization is used. The volume ratio α and the orientation θ of the fibers are assumed to be constant within each element of the finite-element model, but they vary from element to element. The originality of this method relies on the use of variational formulations, which allow to make local minimizations and to accelerate the researching process of the optimal values of θ and α in each element.

THE OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM

Let consider a structure, embedded on the edge (Γ_0), subjected to the volume force \vec{F} and to the surface forces \vec{f} on the rigid edge (Γ_1).

The compliance $S(\theta, \alpha)$, which depends on θ and α on each element is defined by :

$$S(\theta, a) = \int_{\Gamma_1} \vec{f} \vec{u} dl + \int_{\Omega} \vec{F} \vec{u} dV \quad (1)$$

where u is the displacement field.

The response, we wish to minimize with regard to a and θ , is the functional $G(\theta, \alpha)$, which is defined by :

$$G(\theta, a) = S(\theta, a) + k \sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i \quad (2)$$

where k is a positive constant factor which stands for the weight and the cost of the fiber, and α_i the fiber volume fraction on the element i .

Equilibrium equations :

The equilibrium equations of this problem are :

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}}{\partial x_j} + F_i = 0 & \text{on } \Omega & \text{with } \sigma_{ij} = a_{ijkl}(\theta, \alpha) \epsilon_{kl}(u) \\ u_i = 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_0 \\ \sigma_{ij} n_j = 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_l \\ \sigma_{ij} n_j = f_i & \text{on } \Gamma_1 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

with the hypothesis :

$$\begin{cases} a_{ijkh} = a_{ijhk} = a_{hkij}, \text{ uniformly bounded} \\ \exists C_0 > 0, \text{ such as } a_{ijkh} e_{ij} e_{kh} > C_0 e_{ij} e_{kh}, \forall e_{ij} = e_{kh}. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Variational formulations :

The displacement variational formulation of this problem can be written :

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Find } u \in V / a(u, v) = L(v) \quad \forall v \in V \\ & \text{with : } \begin{cases} a(u, v) = \int_{\Omega} a_{ijkl}(\theta, \alpha) \epsilon_{kl}(u) \epsilon_{ij}(v) d\Omega \\ L(v) = \int_{\Gamma_1} f_i v_i d\gamma + \int_{\Omega} F_i v_i d\Omega \\ V = \{v \in H^1(\Omega) / \vec{v}_{/\Gamma_0} = \vec{0}\} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

For $v = u$ we get :

$$a(u, u) = L(u) = S(\theta, \alpha) \quad (6)$$

Let A_{ijkl} be the compliance module tensor, it verifies the hypothesis (4) and :

$$\epsilon_{ij} = A_{ijkl}(\theta, \alpha) \sigma_{kl} \quad (7)$$

The space of the statistically admissible stresses is :

$$\Sigma_{ad} = \left\{ \tau \in H^1(\Omega) / \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_j} + F_i = 0 \text{ on } \Omega, \tau_{ij} n_j = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma_l, \tau_{ij} n_j = f_i \text{ on } \Gamma_1 \right\} \quad (8)$$

As Σ_{ad} is not a vectorial space, the relation (7) is multiplied by $(\tau_{ij} - \sigma_{ij})$, then integrated on Ω , and then the formula of Green is applied to the left term, we get [6]:

$$\int_{\Omega} A_{ijkl} \sigma_{kl} (\tau_{ij} - \sigma_{ij}) d\Omega = 0 \quad (9)$$

Let associate the bilinear form $A(., .)$ to the expression (9), the stress variational formulation is :

$$\text{Find } \sigma \in \Sigma_{ad} / A(\sigma, \tau - \sigma) = 0 \quad \forall \tau \in \Sigma_{ad} \quad (10)$$

Theorem 1 (Double inequality)

If $u \in V$ and $\sigma \in \Sigma_{ad}$ are the displacement solution and the stress field solution, then [6]:

$$\begin{aligned} I(v) & \geq I(u) = -J(\sigma) \geq -J(\tau) \quad \forall v \in V, \forall \tau \in \Sigma_{ad} \\ & \text{with } I(v) = \frac{1}{2} a(v, v) - S(\theta, \alpha) \quad \text{and} \quad J(\tau) = \frac{1}{2} A(\tau, \tau) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The theorem of double inequality leads to :

$$A(\sigma, \sigma) = S(\theta, \alpha) \quad (12)$$

ALGORITHM

Let start with an initial value of (θ, a) , say $(\theta^{(0)}, \alpha^{(0)})$, compute the stress field solution corresponding to $(\theta^{(0)}, \alpha^{(0)})$, say $\sigma^{(0)}$. In a second step, and for any $x \in \Omega$ find $(\theta^{(1)}(x), \alpha^{(1)}(x))$ which realizes locally :

$$\min_{\theta, \alpha} \left[A_{ijhk}(\theta, \alpha) \sigma_{hk}^{(0)} \sigma_{ij}^{(0)} + k \alpha(x) \right] = A_{ijhk}(\theta^{(1)}, \alpha^{(1)}) \sigma_{hk}^{(0)} \sigma_{ij}^{(0)} + k \alpha^{(1)}(x) \quad (13)$$

With this value $(\theta^{(1)}, \alpha^{(1)})$ compute the corresponding stress field solution, say $\sigma^{(1)}$, which, according to (11), satisfies :

$$\min_{\sigma} \left[\int_{\Omega} A_{ijhk}(\theta^{(1)}, \alpha^{(1)}) \sigma_{hk} \sigma_{ij} dx \right] = \int_{\Omega} A_{ijhk}(\theta^{(1)}, \alpha^{(1)}) \sigma_{hk}^{(1)} \sigma_{ij}^{(1)} dx \quad (14)$$

and, consequently :

$$G(\theta^{(1)}, \alpha^{(1)}) \leq G(\theta^{(0)}, \alpha^{(0)}) \quad (15)$$

These calculations can be iterated. At each step the functional $G(\theta, \alpha)$ decreases ; as it is positive it converges [6] to a finite positive value.

Local minimizations allow to accelerate the researching process of the optimal values of θ and α in each element.

NUMERICAL APPLICATIONS

This method has been introduced in the finite element code MODULEF. At this stage, it is applied for panels in plane stresses. The composite plate, where the volume fraction of fibers is a , is transversely isotropic ; the coefficients may be obtained either by homogenization, which gives a very precise result but is not explicite, or by approximate formulas which are the following [7]:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Longitudinal Young modulus :} \quad E_l = \alpha E_l^f + (1 - \alpha)E^m \\ \text{Tranverse Young modulus :} \quad \frac{1}{E_t} = \frac{\alpha}{E_t^f} + \frac{1 - \alpha}{E^m} \\ \text{Shear modulus :} \quad \frac{1}{G_{it}} = \frac{\alpha}{G_{it}^f} + \frac{1 - \alpha}{G^m} \\ \text{Poisson coefficient :} \quad \nu_{it} = \alpha \nu_{it}^f + (1 - \alpha)\nu^m \end{array} \right. \quad (16)$$

The composite material is composed of fibers in kevlar 49 which have the following properties :

$$E_l^f = 130000 \text{ MPa} \quad E_t^f = 5400 \text{ MPa} \quad G_{it}^f = 12000 \text{ MPa} \quad \nu_{it}^f = 0.4$$

and of epoxy resin which has the properties :

$$E^m = 5000 \text{ MPa} \quad G^m = 1700 \text{ MPa} \quad \nu^m = 0.4$$

To illustrate this method, a panel with or without holes, in plane stresses is subjected to different kinds of forces. Three different cases of loading are presented here (Fig.

(1),(3),(5)). The fibers orientations and their volume fraction obtained after one iteration are shown in Fig. (2,4,6). In the third case the table (1) gives the values of the functional G at the initial state and for different iterations, and Fig. (6) and (7) corresponds respectively to the first iteration and to the converge iteration.

• 1st case :

Figure 1: Vertical force Figure 2: Directions and volume fraction of the fibers

• 2nd case :

Figure 3: vertical force Figure 4: Directions and volume fraction of the fibers

• 3rd case :

Figure 5: Linear force

Figure 6: iteration 1

Table 1: Values of G

Nb of iterations	$G(\theta, \alpha)$
$\theta = 0 \quad \alpha = 0,1$	13,3
1	4,27
5	3,89
10	3,87
15	3,83
20	3,83

Figure 7: iteration 20

The solutions are stable and not dependent on the initial values of θ and a . Moreover the use of curvilinear fibers enables to decrease the stresses in the regions where they would be maximal in the case of straight fibers.

Other kinds of panels, subjected to various applied edge loads have been also studied.

CONCLUSION

The method presented here can be generalized to structures with more complex geometry, such as shells. In this aim, the displacement and the stress variational formulations, have already been established for thin shells, and a converging schema has been set up [9].

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